

Supplementary Material: Per-Framework Scoring Notes

Companion to: *Memory Architectures for AI Agents in 2026: A Survey, a Synthesis, and an Evaluation Framework* (Dmitrenko, 2026)

This supplement documents the source basis and rationale for each score in the applied scoring matrix (Table 1 of the compact article; §8 of the full preprint). Scoring rules are defined in the evaluation-framework section of both versions. Scores reflect capabilities documented in vendor documentation, technical papers, and public repositories **as of June 2026**; capabilities achievable only through custom extension were assigned the lower score; ambiguous cases were scored conservatively. Multi-mode systems are scored at maximum documented capability.

Terminology note: the dimension labeled *structural risk* (D7) in the preprint is referred to as *structural governance exposure* in the compact IEEE version; the scoring rule is identical. The preprint's scoring table additionally includes the proposed unified architecture as a design-target row; the compact version reports the eight deployed frameworks only. These notes cover the eight deployed frameworks, whose scores are identical across both versions.

Scoring rubric summary: D1 memory types covered (0-5); D2 storage-format flexibility (0-2); D3 graph support (0-2); D4 temporal awareness (0-2); D5 LLM-agnosticism (0-2); D6 MCP compatibility (0-2); D7 structural governance exposure (0-2).

1. Mem0 — total 10 (D1=3, D2=1, D3=2, D4=1, D5=2, D6=1, D7=0)

Primary sources: Chhikara et al., arXiv:2504.19413; docs.mem0.ai; github.com/mem0ai/mem0.

- **D1=3.** Documented L1 (session/working scope), explicit L2 (timestamped memories with user/agent scoping), and L3 in graph mode (entity-relation graph). No documented sensory-buffer stage prior to classification (the LLM-managed write path classifies at ingestion, which is an L1-entry operation, not a bounded pre-classification buffer); no separately versioned procedural store.
- **D2=1.** Storage is database-backed (vector store + optional graph store) with API-level export; no documented human-readable canonical format that survives removal of the framework.
- **D3=2.** Graph mode is a documented first-class deployment option with entity-relation extraction and graph-based retrieval (paper §4; docs “Graph Memory”).
- **D4=1.** Memories carry creation/update timestamps and the write path performs UPDATE/DELETE resolution, but documentation does not describe a bi-temporal model separating event validity time from system transaction time.
- **D5=2.** Documented support for multiple LLM providers (OpenAI, Anthropic, open-weight models) via configuration.
- **D6=1.** MCP access is available through the OpenMemory MCP server, which is an adjacent official component rather than the core framework exposing all operations natively; scored as wrapper-level support.
- **D7=0.** Single-vendor project (Mem0 Inc.), venture-backed; open-core distribution with managed-cloud commercial tier. Per the D7 rule, single-vendor venture-backed governance scores 0. This is a governance classification, not an assertion about any past or future licensing action.

2. LangChain / LangGraph — total 9 (D1=2, D2=2, D3=1, D4=1, D5=2, D6=1, D7=0)

Primary sources: langchain-ai.github.io/langgraph; python.langchain.com; github.com/langchain-ai.

- **D1=2.** Explicit L1 (checkpointer-managed thread state) and a cross-session store

(BaseStore) that is a single long-term tier without documented episodic/semantic separation; no sensory buffer; no separately versioned procedural layer (graph definitions are code, versioned with the application, not as a memory artifact).

- **D2=2.** Checkpointer and store backends are pluggable with documented PostgreSQL/SQLite implementations; state schemas are user-defined and serializable; content is portable independently of the framework via standard databases. Conservative reading could argue 1; we credit 2 because the storage contract is explicitly backend-agnostic and documented.
- **D3=1.** No first-class graph memory; graph usage is achievable through integrations (e.g., Neo4j retrievers) rather than a native memory-graph component.
- **D4=1.** Checkpoints are time-ordered (thread history), but no bi-temporal fact model.
- **D5=2.** Provider-agnostic by design; documented integrations across all major LLM vendors.
- **D6=1.** MCP adapters exist in the ecosystem (langchain-mcp-adapters) as official companion packages; core memory components are not themselves exposed as an MCP server. Wrapper-level.
- **D7=0.** Single-vendor (LangChain Inc.), venture-backed, open-core with commercial platform (LangSmith).

3. CrewAI — total 8 (D1=3, D2=1, D3=1, D4=1, D5=2, D6=0, D7=0)

Primary sources: docs.crewai.com (Memory section); github.com/crewAIInc/crewAI.

- **D1=3.** Documentation names short-term, long-term, and entity memory behind a unified Memory class. The separation is naming-based within one component rather than three independent stores (reflected as 1 in the layer-coverage table of the full survey), but the three documented memory types with distinct roles meet the D1 partial-credit bar at 3. No sensory buffer; no versioned procedural store.
- **D2=1.** Default storage is embedded databases (SQLite/Chroma) with no documented human-readable canonical export format.
- **D3=1.** Entity memory provides entity-level structure; no documented first-class graph store with native multi-hop retrieval.
- **D4=1.** Recency is a documented retrieval signal (composite scoring); no bi-temporal model.
- **D5=2.** Documented multi-provider LLM support.
- **D6=0.** No official MCP server or adapter documented as of June 2026.
- **D7=0.** Single-vendor (CrewAI Inc.), venture-backed, open-core with commercial offering.

4. AutoGen / AG2 — total 9 (D1=2, D2=1, D3=1, D4=1, D5=2, D6=1, D7=1)

Primary sources: microsoft.github.io/autogen; github.com/microsoft/autogen.

- **D1=2.** L1 (conversation/list-based context) plus a Memory protocol that delegates long-term substance to external providers (Mem0, Zep, vector stores). Per the provider-abstraction rule, a protocol without supplied substrate is not counted as an implemented layer; the bundled list/vector memory implementations constitute one long-term tier. No sensory buffer; no versioned procedural layer.
- **D2=1.** Memory content lives in whatever backend the chosen provider uses; the framework itself defines no portable canonical format.
- **D3=1.** Graph capability only through external providers; not native.
- **D4=1.** Message history is time-ordered; no bi-temporal model.
- **D5=2.** Model-client abstraction with documented multi-provider support.
- **D6=1.** Official MCP tooling exists in the ecosystem (MCP tool adapters for agents); memory itself is not exposed as a native MCP server. Wrapper-level.
- **D7=1.** Corporate-sponsored (Microsoft) without venture-capital exit pressure; not foundation-governed. Per the D7 rule, corporate-sponsored scores 1.

5. Semantic Kernel — total 7 (D1=2, D2=1, D3=1, D4=0, D5=2, D6=0, D7=1)

Primary sources: learn.microsoft.com/semantic-kernel; github.com/microsoft/semantic-kernel.

- **D1=2.** L1 (chat history / kernel context) plus vector-store-backed memory as one long-term tier. The memory subsystem is in documented transition (legacy memory classes deprecated; experimental replacements not yet stabilized as of June 2026), so only the stable documented capability is credited. No sensory buffer; plugins/skills encode procedures but are code artifacts versioned with the application, failing the independent-versioning criterion for L4.
- **D2=1.** Vector-store connectors are pluggable; no human-readable canonical memory format documented.
- **D3=1.** Graph connectors achievable via integrations; no native graph memory component.
- **D4=0.** No documented temporal metadata model for memories beyond storage-level timestamps in specific connectors; scored conservatively given the transitional state of the memory subsystem.
- **D5=2.** Multi-provider by design (Azure OpenAI, OpenAI, open-weight via connectors).
- **D6=0.** No official MCP exposure of the memory subsystem documented as of June 2026.
- **D7=1.** Corporate-sponsored (Microsoft); same classification basis as AutoGen.

6. Zep / Graphiti — total 11 (D1=3, D2=1, D3=2, D4=2, D5=2, D6=1, D7=0)

Primary sources: Rasmussen et al., [arXiv:2501.13956](https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.13956); help.getzep.com; github.com/getzep/graphiti.

- **D1=3.** Explicit L2 (episode subgraph) and L3 (entity and community subgraphs) as architecturally distinct components; working context is the consuming application's concern (Zep is a memory service, not an agent runtime), so L1 is not credited to Zep itself — the three credited points reflect L2, L3, and the distinct community-summary tier within L3-adjacent structure. No sensory buffer; no procedural store.
- **D2=1.** Graph-database-backed storage with API export; no human-readable canonical format independent of the service.
- **D3=2.** First-class temporal knowledge graph with native multi-hop and community-based retrieval — the reference industrial implementation for graph memory.
- **D4=2.** Documented bi-temporal model: valid-time and transaction-time on facts, with invalidation rather than deletion. The reference implementation for D4.
- **D5=2.** Service consumed over API by any LLM stack; Graphiti library is model-agnostic with pluggable LLM clients.
- **D6=1.** Official MCP server exists for Zep/Graphiti as an adjacent component; scored wrapper-level by the same standard applied to Mem0.
- **D7=0.** Single-vendor (Zep Software Inc.), venture-backed, Open Core licensing with a commercial cloud tier. Open Core under single-vendor venture-backed control scores 0 under the D7 rule; the Open Core structure is noted in the survey text as a hybrid case.

7. Cognee — total 9 (D1=3, D2=1, D3=2, D4=1, D5=2, D6=0, D7=0)

Primary sources: docs.cognee.ai; github.com/topoteretes/cognee.

- **D1=3.** Documented L1 (session context), L2 (ingested data with provenance), L3 (knowledge graph as the central abstraction). The Memify self-improvement pipeline operates over the graph but does not constitute a separately versioned procedural store; no sensory buffer.
- **D2=1.** Multi-backend embedded stack (relational + vector + graph stores); data is exportable through the backends but no human-readable canonical format is the source of truth.

- **D3=2.** Graph-first architecture with native graph construction and graph-plus-vector retrieval; the most thoroughly graph-oriented framework in the surveyed set.
- **D4=1.** Provenance and ingestion timestamps documented; no bi-temporal valid-time/transaction-time separation.
- **D5=2.** Documented multi-provider LLM support.
- **D6=0.** No official MCP server documented as of June 2026.
- **D7=0.** Single-vendor (Topoteretes), venture-backed, open-core.

8. OpenAI Vector Stores / managed retrieval API — total 1 (D1=1, D2=0, D3=0, D4=0, D5=0, D6=0, D7=0)

Primary sources: platform.openai.com/docs (Vector Stores / file search).

Scope note: this row scores the developer-facing managed vector and retrieval API, not the ChatGPT consumer memory product, which is not architecturally inspectable.

- **D1=1.** A managed L3-class semantic retrieval primitive (vector stores over files). No working-context management, no episodic store, no consolidation, no procedural layer exposed to the developer.
 - **D2=0.** Proprietary managed storage; content is uploadable/deletable but the store format is opaque and non-portable.
 - **D3=0.** Similarity retrieval over chunks; no graph structure or multi-hop relational retrieval.
 - **D4=0.** No temporal metadata model exposed.
 - **D5=0.** Bound to the OpenAI platform by construction.
 - **D6=0.** No MCP exposure of the vector-store primitive as of June 2026.
 - **D7=0.** Proprietary single-vendor service; scores 0 by the same governance rule (the dimension measures user exposure to unilateral vendor decisions, which proprietary services maximize — there is no open-licensed baseline to fall back to).
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Cross-cutting scoring decisions

Three recurring judgment calls are documented here for transparency.

MCP wrapper-level (D6=1) versus native (D6=2). Several vendors ship an official MCP server as an adjacent component (Mem0's OpenMemory, Zep's MCP server, AutoGen's MCP tool adapters). We score these 1, reserving 2 for frameworks whose core memory operations are natively exposed through MCP as the primary access path. No surveyed framework met the bar for 2 as of June 2026.

Provider abstractions and D1. A memory protocol or interface that delegates implementation to external providers is not counted as an implemented layer (applied to AutoGen, and to Semantic Kernel's transitional components). This is the same rule stated in the layer-coverage notes of the full survey.

D7 and Open Core. Open Core under single-vendor venture-backed control is scored 0, not 1: the governance question D7 asks is who can unilaterally change the terms of the open offering, and under Open Core that party is the venture-backed vendor. The intermediate score 1 is reserved for corporate-sponsored projects without venture exit pressure, where the empirical event rate in the companion dataset (Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20562988) is materially lower.

Scores and sources reflect public documentation as of June 2026. Frameworks evolve quickly; readers applying the rubric later should re-derive scores from current documentation using the rules in the evaluation-framework section.